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Interlaminar Shear Properties of Toughened Carbon Fibre Reinforced Composites

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Fibre Reinforced Polymers for Energy, Climate, Environment and Mobility

E-scooter mobility*

CFRP car wheel **

Airbus A350-900ULR~ (Ultra Long Range)
18.000 km, longest regular air service

Wind power

Source: www.ihk-nuernberg.de

Energy storage

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Sources: **Silvia Hochstätter, ~Website:Airbus,*Paul Langrock/Zenit/laif

Challenge: Materials Design for Tough Thermosets

Thermosetting resins:

- + High stiffness and strength
- + Low creep
- + High adhesion capability
- + Low shrinkage
- + Low viscosity
- + Thermal stability

Challenges, especially:

- Low fracture toughness
- Prone to impact damage

Challenge: Improve Damage Tolerance and Life Time of Composites

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Core-Shell Rubber Particles and Block Copolymers

Core-Shell Rubber (CSR)

Core: rubber
Shell: resin phobic, cross-linked

~20-500 nm

Fibre

CSR toughened Matrix

1 µm

Block Copolymers (BCP)

Bi-block Copolymer

Tri-block Copolymer

B-block

A-block

~1-100nm

Fibre

BCP toughened Matrix

1 µm

Materials & Manufacturing

Resin: *Sika Biresin CR144*

- Base components: **Bisphenol A**
- EEW: 187 g/eq

Hardener: *Huntsman Aradur 917*

- Cycloaliphatic anhydride: Methyl-tetrahydrophthalic anhydride
- Mw: 166 g/mol
- $\eta = 50-100$ mPa s

Accelerator: *Huntsman DY 070*

- 1-Methylimidazol

Fibres:

- Hexcel HexForce G1157 (HTA40 E13)
- Based on AIM 05-01-001-C, Grade B
- Mass: 277 g/m²
- Epoxy coating

Matrix Manufacturing

Materials

Characterisation

Curing

Mixing

Casting

Laminate Manufacturing

Hand lay-up

Autoclaving

Characterisation

Setup: Interlaminar fracture toughness Mode II Shear by End Loaded Split (ELS) test

- Advantages over ENF:
 - No crack propagation correlation via light microscopy
 - Stable test results
- Following ISO 15114
- Precracking: G_{Ic}
- **Sample size:** $L=250$ mm
 $w=25$ mm
 $t=3$ mm
- No. of Samples: 5
- Determination of initiation and propagation values (CBTE method)

$$G_{IIc} = \frac{9P^2 a_e^2}{4b^2 h^3 E_f}$$

ENF: End notched flexure test, P: load,
 a_e : crack length based on compliance reduction,
b: width, h: height, E_f : flex. Modulus,
CBTE: corrected beam theory using effective crack length

Results: Interlaminar fracture toughness Mode II Shear by End Loaded Split (ELS) test

- G_{IIc} increases with rubbery filler concentration
- Hybridized effect show highest values

Results: Interlaminar fracture toughness Mode II Shear by End Loaded Split (ELS) test

- Trendwise good agreement between initiation and propagation values
- G_{IIc} strongly depending on hybridization

Results: Interlaminar fracture toughness Mode II Shear by End Loaded Split (ELS) test

- $G_{Ic,prop}$ correlates to $G_{IIc,prop}$ by a factor of 2
- Shear induced hackle and scallop structure predominant in Mode II

Conclusion

- Interlaminar shear fracture energy of a hybridized, block copolymer - core shell rubber toughened CFRP was enhanced more than a two-fold (208 %) over the unmodified reference system.
- Improvement can be related to a synergistic toughening effect of the matrix by BCP and CSR modifiers.

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